

This was filtered and purified by dissolving in sodium hydroxide solution and reprecipitating by acidification. The precipitated product was filtered off, washed with water and alcohol, dried and weighed (1.2 g.), m. p. 245°.

TABLE I

R.	Acid used.	Acyl derivatives of sulphathiazole.		Acyl derivatives of sulphapyridine.	
		M.p.	Nitrogen % Found. Theo :	M.p.	Nitrogen % Found. Theo :
H	Formic	215°	15.04 14.84	205°	15.33 15.16
CH ₃ -	Acetic	256°		225°	
CH ₃ .CH ₂ -	Propionic	245°	12.98 13.50	217°	14.13 13.77
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂ -	Butyric	250°	13.04 12.92	165°	12.31 12.16
CH ₃ } CH ₃ } CH . CH ₃	<i>iso</i> Valeric	180°	12.47 12.39	191-2°	12.03 12.61
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₆	Caprylic	214°	11.28 11.08	210°	11.33 11.20
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₇	Nonylic	189°	10.71 10.63	186°	11.01 10.80
CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₈	Capric	142°	10.37 10.27	160°	10.15 10.42

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STUDIES IN SULPHANILAMIDES. PART V. N¹-AND N⁴-SUBSTITUTED SULPHANILAMIDES. N⁴-ISO CYCLIC ACYL DERIVATIVES OF SULPHATHIAZOLE AND SULPHAPYRIDINE

BY K. R. DORASWAMY AND P. C. GUHA

Sixteen *iso*-cyclic acyl derivatives of sulphathiazole and sulphapyridine have been prepared.

Although much work has been done on the study of the N⁴-acyclic acyl derivatives of sulphanilamides, it is surprising that only a very few derivatives from aromatic acids have been reported so far and among them only the *p*-nitrobenzoyl derivative is reported to be as active as sulphanilamide itself, and the benzoyl derivative is reported to be inactive. Further, no corresponding derivatives of sulphathiazole and sulphapyridine have so far been made. Therefore, it was considered worth while to prepare a few derivatives of these two drugs with some very common aromatic acids.

These acyl derivatives were prepared by the action of the appropriate acid chloride on sulphathiazole or sulphapyridine in aqueous alkaline solution. The acid chlorides required for this work were prepared by the action of thionyl chloride on the corresponding acids without the use of a solvent. The condensation products were purified by crystallisation from alcohol. They are usually colourless amorphous powders, without sharp melting point and low solubility in water. Their pharmacological examination is awaited.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The following general procedure was followed for the preparation of the derivatives.

Preparation of Benzoylsulphathiazole.—Sulphathiazole (1 g.) was dissolved in 5 c.c. of sodium hydroxide (5%) and benzoyl chloride (0.6 c.c.) was added with good shaking in two or three portions. After each addition the mixture was well shaken. The product separating from the alkaline solution was left to stand for 2 hours with occasional shaking. Then the product was made acidic, and the precipitated benzoyl derivative was filtered off, washed several times with water and alcohol, dried and weighed, yield 1.2 g. Recrystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 250-51°.

TABLE I

R	Acid used.	M.p.	Isocyclic acyl derivatives of sulphathiazole.		Isocyclic acyl derivatives of sulphapyridine.		
			Found.	Theo :	M.p.	Nitrogen % Found. Theo :	
C ₆ H ₅ -	Benzoic	250-51°	11.66	11.69	246-8°	11.83	11.90
<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	<i>p</i> -Chlorobenzoic	240°	10.96	10.67	238°	11.27	10.83
<i>p</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄ -	<i>p</i> -Bromobenzoic	263°	9.22	9.58	215°	9.62	9.72
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ -	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzoic	265°	14.04	13.93	258°	13.87	14.09
<i>p</i> -OMe-C ₆ H ₄ -	<i>p</i> -Methoxybenzoic	185-6°	10.64	10.80	165-6°	11.50	10.96
C ₆ H ₅ .CH=CH-	Cinnamic	253°	10.92	10.91	235°	11.11	11.09
C ₆ H ₅ .CH ₂ -	Phenylacetic	143-5°	11.66	11.26	189°	11.45	11.44
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ -	<i>p</i> -Toluic	265°	11.43	11.28	197-8°	11.13	11.44

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STUDIES IN SULPHANILAMIDES. PART VI. N¹-AND N⁴ SUBSTITUTED SULPHANILAMIDES-AZO-DYES DERIVED FROM SULPHATHIAZOLE AND SULPHAPYRIDINE

BY K. R. DORASWAMY AND P. C. GUHA

Twentysix azo-dyes have been prepared by diazotizing sulphathiazole and sulphapyridine and coupling with aromatic hydroxy and amino compounds.

Although it has not yet been fully proved, the opinion concerning the mode of action of the prontosils (the azo-dyes derived from sulphanilamide) is believed to be the result of the reductive cleavage of the azo-linkage *in vivo*, giving rise to sulphanilamide, which in turn is responsible for the antistreptococcal property.

Further, when these azo-dyes undergo reduction *in vivo*, they give rise not only to sulphanilamide but also to aminophenols and aromatic polyamines. It is known that these aminophenols and aromatic polyamines are oxidised in the system giving rise *in vivo* to quinonoid bodies (Tischler *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940,